
Online Reviews Drive Loyalty: Purchase Decisions Mediate Somethinc Skincare Consumer Behavior

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of the study is to determine how online customer reviews and integrated marketing communications affect the loyalty of consumers to certain skincare products. being aware of how integrated marketing communications and online customer reviews affect consumers' choices to buy certain skincare products. understanding how customer loyalty is influenced by online reviews and integrated marketing communication, which are mediated by choices to buy certain skincare products. This kind of study employs a consumer survey approach using a questionnaire collection technique involving cosmetic consumers in the Bora area. The consumer population in Blora is 232 consumers with a sample of 147 respondents and a nonprobability sampling sample selection method. The SEM PLS 3.2.9 methodology is used in this investigation. The following are the research's conclusions: Customer loyalty to Somethinc Skincare in Blora is positively and significantly impacted by online reviews. Online customer reviews significantly and favorably influence the decision to buy several skincare products. Consumer Loyalty of Somethinc Skincare is positively and significantly impacted by the Online Consumer Review variable. The Consumer Loyalty of Somethinc Skincare in Blora is positively and marginally impacted by the Integrated Marketing Communication variable. The decision to purchase Somethinc Skincare is significantly influenced by integrated marketing communication. Customer loyalty to Somethinc Skincare is positively and significantly impacted by integrated marketing communication. The impact of online customer reviews on customer loyalty may be mitigated by the decision to purchase skincare products. The impact of Integrated Marketing Communication on Customer Loyalty may be mediated by the decision to purchase Somethinc Skincare in Blora.

KEYWORDS: Online Consumer Reviews and Integrated Marketing Communication, Purchasing Decision and Consumer Loyalty

I. INTRODUCTION

The skincare industry in Indonesia has experienced significant development in recent years, along with increasing public awareness of the importance of skin care. This increase is not only marked by the growth in the number of products on the market, but also by the increasing influence of digitalization, especially social media, in shaping consumer preferences and behavior (Silfitri dan Hermawan, 2023). Consumer behavior in forming purchasing decisions makes purchases that result in the formation of loyalty. Loyalty comes from the word loyal which means loyal, the existence of customers with an attitude of loyalty to a brand, store, or supplier, from a positive attitude in purchasing consistently (Gultom et al., 2020). Even if circumstances and marketing campaigns may impact a client's behavior, customer loyalty is the dedication of a consumer to stick with a chosen product or service and re-subscribe or buy it often in the future.

Faster delivery times, superior customer service compared to rivals, and a strong sense of empathy for customers are all factors that affect client loyalty. Loyalty also has characteristics, namely making regular purchases, buying outside the line or service, showing immunity or loyalty from the pull of competition not being affected by other competitors, rejecting other products, recommending to others (Lenteralega et al., 2024). satisfied customers can provide a good basis for purchases and creating customer loyalty.

According to Rini et al., (2023) online consumer reviews are now one of the main sources of information that influence purchasing decisions, where consumers often rely on the experiences and opinions of others in choosing products that suit their needs. On the other hand, marketing through social media, which is packaged in an Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) strategy, is a vital instrument for companies in building brand awareness and consumer loyalty (Welsa et al., 2022).

The role of online consumer reviews and social media in shaping purchasing preferences has been widely discussed in modern marketing literature, However, nothing is known about their precise effects in relation to skincare products (Rini et al., 2023). In the Indonesian market, there hasn't been much research done on how customer evaluations affect choices to buy local goods like

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Somethinc in the face of fiercer competition. Furthermore, little is known about the efficiency of IMC tactics using social media platforms in fostering emotional bonds and persuading customers to buy, particularly when it comes to goods. Due to its unique community features, Blora has a substantial knowledge gap on the ways in which the three elements online customer reviews, IMC on social media, and others interact and affect skincare product purchases.

The purpose of this research is to investigate experimentally how online customer reviews and social media IMC tactics affect consumers' choices to buy Somethinc skincare products in Blora. This research will specifically examine how much online customer reviews affect consumers' decisions to buy skincare goods while accounting for the variety of local market perceptions and preferences. Furthermore, the purpose of this research is to assess how well IMC works on social media to increase brand recognition and influence purchase choices.

Gajanova dan Michulek (2023) stated that although research on consumer behavior and digital marketing has grown rapidly, there is a significant gap in the literature that specifically examines the combined influence of online consumer reviews, IMC on social media in the skincare industry. Most existing studies tend to focus on one or two factors separately, without considering the interaction of the three factors holistically.

Based on Compass 2022, the Somethinc skincare brand is one of the relatively young ones because it was only founded in 2019. However, the Somethinc brand has achieved total sales of IDR 53.2 billion in 2022. This brand offers products that have been adjusted to the skin needs of Indonesians which are also adjusted to the climate and weather conditions in Indonesia. In 2022, the Somethinc brand managed to rank first in the 10 Best-Selling Local Skincare Brands Online and Marketplace according to the 2022 Compass Version. The Somethinc Skincare brand has also beaten its competitor, MS Glow, which has been around for a long time since 2013 and has penetrated the Indonesian market. The MS Glow brand is in 3rd position with total sales reaching IDR 29.4 billion in the period up to 2022.

By providing a thorough approach that integrates three crucial elements of online consumer reviews, IMC on social media, and have not been extensively examined collectively in the context of the skincare industry, this study makes a substantial contribution to the body of research on digital marketing and consumer behavior. According to this research, these three factors taken together have a big impact on what people decide to buy, particularly in a market as dynamic as Indonesia. This research makes a compelling case for the significance of tailored marketing tactics that take into account the unique qualities of local consumers in addition to being pertinent in advancing the theoretical knowledge of the variables influencing purchase choices. As a result, it is anticipated that this research will provide fresh perspectives that will help scholars, industry professionals, and legislators create marketing plans for the skincare and associated sectors.

The findings of earlier studies revealed discrepancies (Gab). For example, Ibrahim and Mamdoh's (2025) study revealed that not all reviews had the same effect, indicating that not all reviews have an impact on choices to buy. Atsila et al. (2020) found that all online customer reviews had a favorable and substantial impact on consumers' choices to buy. According to research by Rini et al. (2023), social media marketing by itself may not have a big impact on choices to buy, which means it has to be combined with other tactics. However, social media has a big impact on how consumers perceive goods, brand awareness, trust, and loyalty, according to study by Prasetya et al. (2024). Therefore, by integrating social media marketing communication and online customer evaluations into a single unit for purchase choices, this research seeks to better investigate the tactics that affect purchasing decisions.

Depending on the problem's background, the following issues may be formulated: 1. Is there an influence of Online Consumer Reviews on consumer loyalty of products and purchasing decisions of Somethinc skincare products in Blora? 2. Is there an influence of IMC conducted through social media on consumer loyalty and purchasing decisions of Somethinc skincare products in Blora? 3. Is there an influence of online consumer reviews conducted through social media and IMC on consumer loyalty mediated by purchasing decisions of Somethinc skincare products in Blora

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Kotler and Keller (2016), client loyalty is the resolve of consumers to continue purchasing and supporting goods and services they find appealing. The following are the metrics used to gauge client loyalty, according to Puspita (2022): 1) Refer to others. 2) Experiment with other potential product categories. and 3) is among the greatest substitutes among the available items. Gitosudarmo (2018) asserts that a person's purchase choice is a model of their attitude about a product or service, making it an excellent tool for gauging their sentiments toward a certain brand group, product, or service. The desire to acquire a product is what drives a purchase choice, and it will occur if a buyer is swayed by the product's quality and information (Dharmmesta et al., 2017).

Prakosa and Tjahjaningsih (2021) list the following as the first of numerous indicators used to measure buying decisions: a. 1) Problem Recognition, 2) Information Search, 3) Alternative Evaluation, 4) Purchase Decision, and 5) Post-Purchase Behavior.

Online consumer reviews are feedback provided by consumers about products or services they have purchased, usually published on e-commerce platforms or social media. These reviews can be in the form of text, star ratings, or videos that show the consumer's experience with the product (Hasan, 2024). Online Consumer Review Indicators according to Pan (2023) are used as

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follows: 1) Influence of Reviews, 2) Influence of Positive Reviews; 3) Influence of Negative Reviews, 4) Reviews versus Ads, 5) Number of Reviews, 6) Influence of Influencers.

IMC aims to convey consistent and coherent messages to consumers through various communication channels (Parwitasari 2023). Indicators used to measure the effectiveness of IMC on social media according to Hariyanto dan Trisunarno (2020). include: 1) Social Media, 2) Promotion Consistency, 3) Promotion Active, 4) Relevant Promotion Campaigns that answer needs, 5) Content Clarity, 6) Influencer Promotion

III. METHODS

The type of research uses a survey conducted on consumers using a data collection technique using a questionnaire involving cosmetic consumers in the Bora area. This study, which is called the population, is consumers in Bora as many as 232 consumers sourced from the Gaaksi Cosmetics Store with a sampling technique based on Slovin's opinion so that 147 respondents were obtained and a nonprobability sampling sample selection method for the purposive sampling type with consideration (judgement sampling) which refers to a sort of non-random sample selection when information is gathered based on certain factors. The Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) PLS technique is used in line research. Smart PLS 3.2.9 program for partial least squares (PLS). A multivariate statistical method for comparing many independent and dependent variables is partial least squares (PLS) analysis. In order to provide a complete image of the model, SEM is a multivariate statistical analysis approach that is used to test for the existence of complicated direct or indirect effect, both unidirectional and non-directional (Hair et al., 2017).

IV. RESULTS

The research, which used samples with respondent characteristics based on gender, revealed that, with 95 respondents, or 64.63% of the total, female respondents were more prevalent than male respondents, with 52 respondents, or 35.37% of the total. It may be inferred that a greater proportion of the study's respondents 95, or 64.63% were female. The characteristics of respondents by age revealed that the majority of respondents (56 individuals, or 38.10% of the total) were between the ages of 26 and 34, while the fewest respondents (26 individuals, or 17.69%) were above the age of 45. We may deduce that 56 individuals (38.10%) were responders who were between the ages of 26 and 34. The largest number of respondents (62, or 42.18%) had only completed S1 schooling, while the smallest percentage (14, or 9.52%) had only completed elementary or junior high school. Consequently, it may be said that responses with S1 education were more dominant in this study, namely 62 respondents or 42.18%. Respondent characteristics show that a total of 147 respondents were obtained, with the majority of the work being self-employed, amounting to 40 people with a percentage of 27.21%, and the least number of workers, amounting to 5 people (3.40%).

1. Measurement Model Test (Outer Model).

In data analysis with SEM-PLS using the outer model, there is a loading factor that is used to show the correlation between indicators between construct indicators.

a. Validity Test

The outer loading value may be used to evaluate convergent validity. When an indicator of a variable satisfies the criteria of an outer loading value >0.70 , it is said to have a high degree of validity and convergent validity. The findings of this study's validity test for the outer loading value are as follows:

Table 1. Outer Loading Results

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Items</i>	<i>Outer loading</i>	<i>Conclusion</i>
Consumer Loyalty	Y1.1	0,799	Valid
	Y1.2	0,845	Valid
	Y1.3	0,877	Valid
Buying decision	Z1.1	0,914	Valid
	Z1.2	0,784	Valid
	Z1.3	0,914	Valid
	Z1.4	0,778	Valid
	Z1.5	0,860	Valid
Online Consumer Review	x1.1	0,816	Valid
	x1.2	0,786	Valid
	x1.3	0,895	Valid
	x1.4	0,804	Valid
	x1.5	0,721	Valid

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	x1.6	0,749	Valid
IMC	x2.1	0,840	Valid
	x2.2	0,862	Valid
	x2.3	0,903	Valid
	x2.4	0,797	Valid
	x2.5	0,810	Valid
	x2.6	0,842	Valid

Source: Processed data, 2025

None of the indicators in this study had an outer loading value less than 0.70, according to the research findings shown in Table 1. Every indicator displays an outside loading value greater than 0.70, which means that these indicators meet the convergent validity criteria and can be stated as valid indicators.

Table 2. Average Variance Extracted (AVE) Results

Variable	AVE
Online Consumer Review	0,635
IMC	0,711
Buying decision	0,726
Consumer Loyalty	0,707

Source: Processed data, 2025

All of the variables in this study had Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values larger than 0.5, according to the research findings shown in Table 2. This suggests that each variable has sufficient convergent validity, meaning that over half of the variation of the measured indicators can be explained by the concept.

One of the three methods for measuring discriminant validity is to use the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT). HTMT :

Table 3. Discriminant Validity Test – HTMT

Variable	IMC	Buying decision	Consumer Loyalty
IMC			
Buying decision	0,570		
Consumer Loyalty	0,557	0,867	
Online Consumer Review	0,359	0,538	0,597

Source: Processed data, 2025

Overall, the variables in this study have strong discriminant validity since each variable's HTMT value is less than 0.90, according to the research findings from Table 3.

b. Reliabilty Test

c. Uji Reliabilitas

One component used to evaluate the dependability value of variable indicators is composite reliability. If the composite reliability value is more than 0.7, the variables are considered to fulfill composite reliability. The composite reliability results for each variable are as follows.

Table 4. Composite reliability results

Variable	Composite reliability
Online Consumer Review	0,912
IMC	0,936
Buying decision	0,930
Consumer Loyalty	0,878

Source: Processed data, 2025

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The composite reliability value for all variables is over 0.7, indicating that all variables are dependable, according to the data above.

The Cronbach's Alpha Value may be used to reinforce the reliability test using composite reliability mentioned above. If a variable's Cronbach's Alpha value is more than 0.7, it is considered dependable. The Cronbach's Alpha values for each variable are as follows.

Table 5. Cronbach's Alpha results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha
Online Consumer Review	0,888
IMC	0,920
Buying decision	0,904
Consumer Loyalty	0,795

Source: Processed data, 2025

All of the variables' Cronbach's Alpha values are over 0.7, indicating their reliability, according to the data above.

2. Inner Model Analysis

This inner model research will use testing with a structural measurement model or inner model consisting of the Coefficient of Determination (R^2) and Effect Size (f^2),

Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

Table 6. Results of R Square (R^2)

Variable	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Buying decision	0,414	0,406
Consumer Loyalty	0,716	0,710

Source: Processed data, 2025

According to the aforementioned findings, 0.406, or 40.6%, of choices are influenced by online consumer reviews and integrated marketing communications. This finding indicates that factors other than this have an impact on 59.4%. On the other hand, Integrated Marketing Communication and Online Consumer Reviews have a 71% (0.710) impact on consumer loyalty characteristics. This finding indicates that factors other than this have an impact on 29%.

Effect Size (f^2)

Based on the data that has been done using smart PLS 3.0, the F-square value (f^2) was obtained as follows:

Table 7. Effect Size (f^2)

Variable	Buying decision	Consumer Loyalty
IMC	0,269	0,004
Buying decision		1,141
Online Consumer Review	0,195	0,050

Source: Processed data, 2025

According to the aforementioned findings, there is a moderately strong correlation between purchasing decisions and customer loyalty (1.141). There is a 0.269 (big) correlation between Integrated Marketing Communication and Purchasing Decisions, and a 0.004 (small) correlation between Consumer Loyalty and Purchasing Decisions. The relationship between Online Consumer Reviews and Purchasing Decisions is 0.050 which is classified as moderate, while the relationship between Consumer Loyalty and Consumer Loyalty is 0.195 which is classified as large.

3. Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing of research can use path coefficients or inner models that indicate the level of strength of the relationship or the level of significance between constructs and empirical T values. The use of Path Coefficients for testing has the aim of testing the relationship of structural models that are part of the hypothesis in research with standard values ranging from (-1) to (+1). While

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the T-Test is part of the inner model hypothesis testing with the condition that the t-statistic value obtained must be greater than 1, and the significance level limit is 5% or the expected p-value is less than 0.05.

a. Direct Influence Testing.

Table 8. Direct Influence Path Results

Direct Influence Path	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Conclusion
Online Consumer Review -> Consumer Loyalty	0,139	0,138	0,036	3,886	0,000	Significant
Online Consumer Review -> Buying decision	0,360	0,359	0,061	5,942	0,000	Significant
IMC -> Consumer Loyalty	0,039	0,039	0,046	0,856	0,393	No Significant
IMC -> Buying decision	0,423	0,431	0,076	5,575	0,000	Significant
Buying decision -> Consumer Loyalty	0,744	0,744	0,058	12,793	0,000	Significant

Source: Processed data, 2025

b. Indirect Influence Testing

Table 9. Indirect Influence Testing Results

Pengaruh Tidak Langsung	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Conclusion
Online Consumer Review -> Buying decision -> Consumer Loyalty	0,268	0,264	0,044	6,159	0,000	Significant
IMC -> Buying decision -> Consumer Loyalty	0,315	0,318	0,054	5,817	0,000	Significant

Source: Processed data, 2025

4. Discussion

a. The Influence of Online Consumer Reviews on Consumer Loyalty of Somethinc Skincare in Blora

The study's findings demonstrate that online customer reviews significantly and favorably affect Blora consumers' loyalty to Somethinc Skincare. According to these findings, the first hypothesis that online customer reviews significantly and favorably impact the loyalty of consumers to certain skincare products in Blora has been validated. The findings of this research support those of Lisnawati et al. (2021) and Listiani & Arifin (2024), which demonstrated the substantial impact of online consumer reviews on customer loyalty.

Electronic Word of Mouth (eWOM), which is a direct opinion from someone and not an advertising, comes from a variety of sources, including the quality of the items or the customer's experience purchasing them and reviews (Hariyanto dan Trisunarno, 2020). Because they are provided willingly by consumers who have actually bought the product, customer reviews are considered relevant. One of the elements influencing choices to buy is customer reviews. However, the more reviews there are, the less certain it will be to determine purchasing decisions because there are many factors that are the reasons for the decision. Consumer reviews dare (OCR) play an important role in shaping purchasing decisions, especially since users usually rely on the experiences of other consumers before purchasing a product.

b. The Influence of Online Consumer Reviews on Somethinc Skincare Purchasing Decisions in Blora

The study's findings demonstrate that online customer reviews significantly and favorably influence Blora consumers' decisions to buy certain skincare products. These findings demonstrate the validity of the second hypothesis, which holds that online consumer reviews significantly and favorably influence some skincare purchase decisions in Blora; the higher the online consumer review, the higher the purchasing decision. These findings support the findings of Welsa et al. (2022), Atsila et al. (2020), and Mahendra dan Edastama (2022), which demonstrate the importance of online consumer reviews in influencing purchase decisions. Because customers often depend on other consumers' experiences before making a purchase, online consumer reviews (OCR) have a significant influence on how people make judgments about what to buy.

c. The Influence of Integrated Marketing Communication on Consumer Loyalty of Somethinc Skincare in Blora

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The Consumer Loyalty of Somethinc Skincare in Blora is positively and marginally impacted by the Integrated Marketing Communication variable. Based on these findings, the third hypothesis that Integrated Marketing Communication significantly and favorably affects Somethinc Skincare's customer loyalty in Blora has not been validated. These findings contradict those of Oktafiani and Sunardi's (2021) research (Safitri et al., 2022). Dan (Nuraini et al., 2021) discovered that, while not demonstrated, integrated marketing communication had a favorable and large impact on customer loyalty. Through a variety of communication platforms, IMC on social media enables businesses to establish direct connections with consumers. According to Rini et al.'s research from 2023, social media marketing raises brand recognition, which then contributes to Consumer Loyalty. IMC is also able to build emotional relationships between brands and consumers.

d. The Influence of Integrated Marketing Communication on Somethinc Skincare Purchasing Decisions in Blora

The study's findings indicate that Blora's decisions to purchase somethinc skincare products are positively and significantly impacted by the integrated marketing communication variable. Because the higher the Integrated Marketing Communication, the higher the Somethinc Skincare Purchasing Decision in Blora, these results support the fourth hypothesis, which claims that Integrated Marketing Communication has a positive and significant effect on Somethinc Skincare Purchasing Decisions in Blora. The findings of this research are in line with those of studies by Makahimpong (2023) and Putri dan Angraini (2024), which demonstrate that IMC on social media significantly influences purchasing decisions. Through a variety of communication platforms, IMC on social media enables businesses to establish direct connections with consumers. According to Rini et al.'s research from 2023, social media marketing raises brand recognition, which then contributes to purchasing decisions. IMC is also able to build emotional relationships between brands and consumers.

e. The Influence of Purchasing Decisions on Consumer Loyalty

The study's findings show that consumer loyalty to Somethinc Skincare in Blora is positively and significantly impacted by the purchasing decision variable. Because the greater the purchasing decision, the higher the consumer loyalty, these findings support the fifth hypothesis, which claims that purchasing decisions have a favorable and substantial impact on consumer loyalty of somethinc skincare in Blora. This study's findings are in line with those of Wahyuni & Sulastri (2020) and Riyanto & Helmy (2020), who found a direct and substantial relationship between staff purchasing decisions and consumer loyalty.

f. The Influence of Online Consumer Reviews on Consumer Loyalty Mediated by Purchasing Decisions

Therefore, it can be concluded that purchasing decisions mediate the impact of online consumer reviews on consumer loyalty. The study's findings showed that purchasing decisions can mediate the influence of online consumer reviews on consumer loyalty of Somethinc Skincare in Blora.

According to these findings, the sixth hypothesis that "The Influence of Online Consumer Reviews on Consumer Loyalty is Mediated by Purchasing Decisions of Somethinc Skincare in Blora" has been validated and has a favorable impact since the more purchasing decisions made, the more these reviews can influence consumer loyalty. Online consumer reviews have a significant impact on consumer loyalty mediated by purchasing decisions, according to research by Lisnawati et al. (2021) and Listiani dan Arifin (2024), Welsa et al. (2022), Atsila et al. (2020), and Mahendra dan Edastama (2022). These findings are in line with those of these studies.

Because customers often depend on the experiences of other consumers before making a purchase, online consumer reviews (OCR) have a big influence on what people decide to buy. According to research, although bad reviews might reduce customer loyalty, good evaluations can boost consumer confidence in a product.

g. The Influence of Integrated Marketing Communication on Consumer Loyalty Mediated by Purchasing Decisions

According to the study's findings, the Purchasing Decision variable has the ability to moderate the impact of Integrated Marketing Communication on Blora consumers' loyalty to Somethinc Skincare. According to these findings, the fifth hypothesis that "The Influence of Integrated Marketing Communication on Consumer Loyalty is Mediated by Purchasing Decisions of Somethinc Skincare in Blora" has been validated and has a favorable impact since better purchasing decisions can mitigate the impact of Integrated Marketing Communication on consumer loyalty. The findings of this study align with those of Putri dan Angraini (2024) and Makahimpong (2023), who discovered that Integrated Marketing Communication significantly and favorably influences consumer loyalty. Additionally, the Integrated Marketing Communication variable influences consumer loyalty through the mediation variable of purchasing decisions.

h. IMC on social media allows brands to connect directly with audiences through various communication channels. Research Rini et al., (2023) states that social media marketing increases brand awareness, which then contributes to purchasing decisions. IMC is also able to build emotional relationships between brands and consumers

V. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the analysis, the following conclusions may be drawn from this study: 1. Somethinc Skincare's customer loyalty is positively and significantly impacted by online reviews. These findings demonstrate that the first hypothesis, according to which online consumer reviews significantly and favorably impact Somethinc Skincare customers' loyalty, is correct. 2. The second hypothesis is validated since online consumer reviews significantly and favorably influence Blora consumers' decisions to buy certain skincare products. Consumer Loyalty of Somethinc Skincare is positively and significantly impacted by the Online Consumer Review variable. 3. The Consumer Loyalty of Somethinc Skincare in Blora is positively and marginally impacted by the Integrated Marketing Communication variable. Based on these findings, the third hypothesis that Integrated Marketing Communication has a favorable and negligible impact on Somethinc Skincare Blora's customer loyalty has not been validated. 3. Consumer Loyalty of Somethinc Skincare is positively and marginally impacted by the Integrated Marketing Communication variable. According to these findings, the third hypothesis that integrated marketing communication has a favorable and negligible impact on Somethinc Skincare customers' loyalty has not been validated. 4. The fourth hypothesis is validated because integrated marketing communication significantly influences consumers' decisions to buy somethinc skincare products in Blora. In the meanwhile, Somethinc Skincare's customer loyalty is positively and significantly impacted by integrated marketing communication. 5. The impact of online customer reviews on customer loyalty may be mitigated by decisions to buy certain skincare products in Blora. The study's findings demonstrated a complete mediation connection, meaning that the Purchase Decision variable acts as a mediator between the Online Consumer Review and Consumer Loyalty variables. 6. The impact of integrated marketing communication on customer loyalty may be mediated by Blora skincare consumers' decisions to purchase certain products. The study's findings demonstrated a partial mediation connection, meaning that the Purchase Decision variable acts as a mediator between the Integrated Marketing Communication variable and the Consumer Loyalty variable.

SUGGESTIONS

Based on this study, the following recommendations are made for future researchers: 1. Including research objects to compare the findings with those of other related fields in order to maximize the research outcomes. 2. Adjusting the study model by adding factors like communication variables, and completing the independent variables by increasing the number of variables in order to broaden the knowledge in the area of management, particularly human resource management. 3. In order to eliminate the proportion of the independent variable's effect on the dependent variable, it is intended that future research would include additional variables and more comprehensive analytic techniques.

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